

NEW MEDIA AND THE PROLIFERATION OF FAKE NEWS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The emergence of new media technologies brought about the transformation of society in virtually all aspects of national life. It has collapsed time and distance barrier in communication and thereby democratising information communication apparatus. The increasing use of new media has raised concerns in several quarters on its implications to heighten the spread of fake news in society. The study utilises library research technique to gather data for the study while Inoculations theory and Conspiracy theory were the theoretical framework that guided the study. The paper argues that the proliferation of new media technologies has led to the dissemination of fake news in Nigeria. The study finds that new media technologies was being used to spread fake news and misinformation in key critical areas like political communication, war against insurgency, and the promotion of ethnic sentiments among Nigerians. The study recommends that government and tech companies educate the people on the mechanism of facts checking so that they can identify false and misleading information.

Keywords: Fake news, new media, communication, mass media

Introduction

Journalism is in a state of considerable flux. New digital platforms have unleashed innovative journalistic practices that enable novel forms of communication and greater global reach than at any point in human history. But on the other hand, disinformation and hoaxes that are popularly referred to as “fake news” are accelerating and affecting the way individuals interpret daily developments. The spread of misinformation on web pages as well as the new media platforms has assumed a worrisome proportion. Fake news is now considered by many as a threat to peace, order and stability across the globe.

New media is said to be very important to the entire media industry. What the new media contribute to the industry is immeasurable. In the areas of news gathering, processing as well as dissemination, the new media is performing remarkable tasks. The rippling effect of this is that it also spread misinformation at the speed of light. Van der Linden, Maibach, Cook, Leiserowitz & Lewandowsky (2017a) opine that false information can reach large audiences by spreading rapidly from one individual to another. Wong (2019) also lend credence to the argument that social media (which is a type of the new media) help in the spread of fake news.

Literature abounds as to the main reasons responsible for the spread of fake news. Majority of these literature points to human influence. In other words, the spread of fake news is most often human-assisted (see Steinmetz, 2018; Anderson & Rainie, 2017). What this mean is that people who spread misinformation used the “share” button on their social media pages before double-checking to realise they just shared fake news.

The spread of fake news is assuming a dangerous dimension as those who share misinformation do not realise there is the need to quickly send out a rebuttal once it dawned on them that a wrong has been done. This partly is responsible for why fake news is said to be taking a dangerous turn. In other cases, those who know the need for rebuttals usually get to realise that in most cases, the damage may have been done already. Recently, *Pew Research Centre* based in the United States came up with a research and according to the findings, adult in the US who prefer to get their news through social media are more likely to share fake news than those who prefer to get news via conventional methods such as newspapers, TV or websites, (see Robertson, 2016; Wong, 2019). A similar research also revealed that those who rely on social media are less engaged and less knowledgeable, (Mitchell, Jurkowitz, Oliphant & Shearer, 2020).

It is pertinent to note that owners of tech companies’ especially social media platforms – *Facebook, Twitter, Instagram* amongst others have embarked on moves to combat the phenomenon but with little success as their efforts have not stopped people from sharing misinformation, (Wong, 2019). It is difficult to achieve this because the social media space remains the most difficult to censor. Selective policing cannot also be effective as participants on new media forums or users of new media platforms could appear to be anonymous if they so wish.

The traditional media have been identified as one at the receiving end and also part of the solutions to the spread of fake news. The society looks up to the media to find a solution to the spread of fake news. This is because fake news (to an extent) are known to be diminishing credibility of the media and the role of social media themselves. People tend to consume fake news on social media platforms and then turn around to blame the media in general. This is one way the concept of fake news is diminishing media trust, (Madrid-Morales & Wasserman, 2019). The paper looks at new media and the proliferation of fake news within the Nigerian social milieu and how the spread of fake news has affected some critical aspects of the country.

Conceptual Review

New media is a term that reflects the emergence of digital, comprised or networked information and communication technologies in the later part of the 20th century. Such technologies that are referred to as “new media” are digital, often having characteristics of being manipulated, networkable, comprehensible, dense, interactive and impartial, (Ekpemo & Igbozuruike, 2018).

The tools mainly are but not limited to smart phones, tablet computers, and other mobile devices capable of accessing the Internet. The new media could also be referred to as the digital media that can be found on the new devices, such as news app, blogs and websites, social media postings and chats, feeds, online newspapers and magazines, flash animations videos and podcasts. In this regard, Ekpemo and Igbozuruike (2018) state that:

What is new about the new media is that they are digital, they are linked and cross linked with each other and the information they mediate is very easily processed, stored, transformed, retrieved, linked and perhaps most radical of all easily searched for and accessed. (p.8-9)

To Nnamuo and Nwafor (2019), the new media refer to all platforms powered by the Internet which find its base on the emergence of the new information and communication technologies. They listed the new media forms to include: social networking sites like *Facebook*, *YouTube*, *WhatsApp*, *2go*, *WeChat* etc., mobile/cell phones, wikis, blogs, online newspapers, webcasts, video streaming among many others.

The new media are quite unique kind of technologies with their numerous benefits as well as advantages. The power they wield, the anonymity they possess and allow, make them easy tools for the spread of fake news and propaganda messages. The new media are highly interactive platforms, ubiquitous and have multiplicity of use and open-ended character. That serves as the propeller that moves fake news business. Those whose preoccupation is to mislead people to take negative actions find the new media tool useful to perpetuate such acts.

Fake news as a concept has no universally accepted definitions. Several authors have provided explanations to the term. However, since the 2016 US election, the word has received more definitions. Carson (2019) observed that the word “fake news” besides being a favourite term of Donald Trump – the man who won the 2016 US elections, it was also named 2017’s word of the year. However, we shall attempt to define the term as it is used in this study. Fake news is the deliberate misinformation about an issue or a matter. McGonagle (2017, p.203) defined fake news as “information that has been deliberately fabricated and disseminated with the intention to deceive and mislead others into believing falsehoods or doubting verifiable facts; it is disinformation that is presented as, or is likely to be perceived as, news.”

Theoretical Underpinning

Theories give clarifications to concepts and place them in perspectives. They elucidate as well as give light to grey areas placing issues side-by-side existing theories in order to test theoretical positions. In relations to that, this study draws its strength from the Inoculations theory and Conspiracy theory.

The spread of fake news amplified through the new media can be modeled much like the spread of a viral contagion (Kucharski, 2016). Inoculation theory provides a thought-provoking solution to viral contagion spread by offering the possibility of a “vaccine” against fake news (van der Linden, Laiserowitz, Rosenthal & Maibach, 2017).

The theory was originally developed by William McGuire (1964) in an attempt to induce attitudinal resistance against all form of persuasion and propaganda, in a way likened to biological immunisation. Illustratively, it is known to science that a weakened dose of a virus can be built into an injection to activate the production of antibodies once introduced to a body. This is usually done with the sole purpose of building resistance against future infection from the virus. In the same vein, inoculation theory postulates such can be actualised with what it termed “mental antibodies” and information. “In other words, by preemptively exposing people to a weakened version of a (counter)-argument, and by subsequently refuting that argument, attitudinal resistance can be conferred against future persuasion attempts,” (Papageorgis & McGuire, 1961) as cited in Roozenbeek and Van der Linden (2018).

There is the affective and cognitive component in the inoculation process often referred to as “threat” and “refutational preemption” (McGuire, 1964) as cited in Roozenbeek and van der Linden (2018). The role of perceived risk or “threat” is largely motivational and refers to the recognition that one’s attitude on an issue is vulnerable to attack, whereas “reputational preemption” is concerned with providing people with specific arguments to help resist persuasion attempts. Inoculation has a rich history in communication (see Compton, 2013).

Although research to date has mostly found subtle differences between different inoculation procedures (Banas & Rains, 2010), the hypothesis that inoculation could provide “umbrella protection” against the risk of fake news is intriguing because such general immunity avoids the need for tailored content. Evidence for cross-attitudinal protection has also surfaced in other contexts (e.g. Parker, Rains, & Ivanov, 2016) and van der Linden *et al.* (2017b) found that while a general warning was less effective than a tailored message, it still conferred significant resistance against attempts to politicise science (see also Cook, Lewandowsky & Ecker, 2017). Accordingly, we draw on the inoculation metaphor and approach in the present study. Inoculation theory is relevant to this study as it seeks to assert how people receive fake news through new media. The effects such fake news has on people and their response as well.

Conspiracy theory on the other hand is seen as an attempt to provide explanation to the issues behind significant socio-political events or circumstances with claims

of secret plots by powerful actors, (Keeley, 1999) as cited in Douglas, Uscinski, Sutton, Cichocka, Nefes, Ang and Deravi (2019). Conspiracy theory is not exclusive to governments alone but to power individuals or groups. McKenzie-McHarg (2018) cited in Douglas *et al.* (2019) observed that whereas a conspiracy has to do with a true causal chain of events, conspiracy theory refers to an allegation of conspiracy that may or may not be true.

There are cases where people have certain belief about an issue in such case; it is “conspiracy belief”. According to Enders and Smallpage (2018), about 60% Americans believe that John F. Kennedy was assassinated by the CIA and even a larger number of people continue to sustain such belief. In Nigeria, for instance, a majority of persons believe that the country is being run by Jibrin Al-Sudani – a man from Sudan following the rumoured death of Muhammadu Buhari in 2017. This is known as conspiracy belief. Conspiracy theory is applied to this paper as it helps us understand fake news and how it is possible to present issues that are not true as though they are real in order to either divert people’s attention or promote a particular cause.

Methodology

The study employed library research technique to gather data for the work, where most of the information sources were drawn from previous literature. Thus, secondary sources were utilised to gather the data. The data were basically gathered from textbooks, journals, periodicals and online materials.

Literature Review

The importance of the mass media as providers of information in period of crisis and national events has been discussed extensively by media scholars. Fake news often thrives during period of crisis, campaigns and national or international events. As part of their duties, the media of communication must provide in-depth coverage and updates of issues in order to meet the information need of the people.

Apuke and Omar (2020) studied the motivation behind the spread of fake news during the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. The researchers found that altruism was the major factor that heralded the sharing of fake news on COVID-19. Further findings of the study reveal that social media users’ motivation for sharing information on the cyber space was to provide knowledge to other persons who may be ignorant of certain health information that would constitute health dangers to their health. However, these persons do not care to verify the authenticity of information before posting it online hence the proliferation of fake news during the pandemic in Nigeria.

In a research by Wasserman and Madris-Morales (2019) to investigate how fake news influences political campaigns in parts of Africa. The researchers polled nearly 1,900 highly educated, urban residents and middle class people from Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa. The study found that 93% Nigerians, 90% Kenyans and 76% South

Africans are of the opinion that they are well exposed to fake news about politics of their country on a fairly regular basis. The researchers discovered that respondents in the study do not trust information on social media platforms because most of the content of the information were filled with fake news. Even though the study recognizes the power of new media technologies to spread information on a fast lane, the study recommended that measures should be taken by government to educate citizens on how to control the way they use their social media devices.

In a study to ascertain the impact of fake news on society in the era of social media, Ngwainmbi (2018) found that the benefits from technological advancement in new media are numerous that it also comes with its challenges one of which is the spreading of false and unreliable information. Ngwainmbi (2018) study further examined the implications of fake news for nation building between developed countries and developing countries of the world. His findings show that while phony news sharing is more common in industrialised nations because of users' easy access to portable devices, those in developing countries share news content on a massive scale, in part, because they do not have the resources to filter real news from fake news. The researcher argues that users of social media platforms in both parts of the world may be less interested in working to decipher phony news content because it provides intrigue. The study claims that fake news reporting shared on social media can have significant implications on nation-building, particularly the socio-economic advancement of countries.

Banerjee and Haque (2018) examined the spread of fake news in India and how it has been manipulated by political figures to foster their selfish interest in the country. Their study demonstrated that the menace of fake news has been exploited by Indian politicians to spread hate speech and fake news in the country. For instance, in 2018 a video was widely circulated of a large crowd of supporters celebrating Pakistan's win in a cricket match in India. The message claimed that the Indian Muslims were being traitors for supporting their arch-rivals. In reality the video was shot in Pakistan and the people were from Pakistan itself. The video was posted on Facebook and Youtube multiple times and garnered views and propagated the idea that Indian Muslims are anti-national. This development led to some pockets of crisis in India.

Yaraghi (2019) in his study describes misinformation on social media as a negative aspect of our culture, making the world less informed and disintegrating confidence. The study noted that web-based companies ignore their responsibility of cross checking facts before publishing content on their websites, but due to the rising cases of fake information they have devised a series of computerised and human-driven procedures for the promotion, editing and filtering of published content, as these measures have become primary sources of knowledge for an overwhelming number of users.

New media, new audience and the proliferation of fake news

New media does a lot to the practice of journalism the world over. It has changed the face of the profession. The new media has the potential of reaching larger audiences in a shorter period of time and often leads to a greater interaction between journalists and the readers or viewers. Journalists now make use of new media technologies to post news content while the readers equally make use of the same to access news. The fact that new media are highly interactive platforms with their emergence, the former recipient of news who used to be receivers are now active creators of content.

Again, it is important to state that the emergence of new media technologies equally redefines the concept of media audience today. Today's digital audience considerably removed barriers to news production and signaled "the shift of the tools of production to the people formerly known as the audience," who became co-producers, of content, including news - a function and practice described as 'produsage'. They initially built audiences via email and chat-rooms before social media platforms dramatically amplified their reach, (See Gilmore, 2004; Bruns, 2008; Posetti, 2018).

The arrival of social media has also been a big issue to authentic news dissemination. In many countries, by the late-2000s, *Twitter* and *Facebook* had joined *YouTube* as major social media platforms, wielding considerable influence on the practices and professional identities of journalists (especially regarding verification, audience engagement, and the clash of the personal and public spheres that occur on social platforms), and the distribution of content. Beginning from individuals building networks around trust, and then peer-to-peer distribution of content (particularly on social media platform - Facebook) thus traditional methods of content dissemination was challenged, (See Posetti, 2009; Posetti, 2013; Posetti, 2018).

Social media users became active creators of media content as well as streaming that of news services and journalists without any form of mediation. Since media contents are distributed through seemingly reliable platforms or network, it saw an increase in the spread of inaccurate, false, malicious and propagandistic content masquerading as news, (Posetti, 2018). Researchers such as Bakir & McStay (2017) have discovered that media contents considered as emotive, and others shared by a friend, or close family member is more likely to be redistributed by users on social media platforms. It is equally on record that traditional media organisations and journalists make use of social media platforms to generate and distribute news and also engage their audience because of the need to be present in virtual environments with massive audience presence. Posetti (2018) avers that even with such presence, news organisation create filter bubbles or echo chambers which has reduced many individual users' exposure to alternative views and verified information.

New media has liberalised everything news. This is not without some of the downsides. Posetti (2018, p.60) captured some of these pitfalls as follows:

- i. Increased likelihood of disinformation and misinformation going viral with distribution amplified by ‘trust networks’¹⁰¹ and emotional reactions (e.g. triggered by confirmation bias).
- ii. The ability of governments and other agencies to side-step news media interrogation and verification by ‘going direct to audiences’ to avoid scrutiny. There is evidence of increased manipulation of the power of social media by those seeking to influence election outcomes and public policy.
- iii. Sensational information is more likely to be shared.
- iv. The inability to easily pull back or correct disinformation and misinformation.

Whereas the issue of fake news has always been with us, the new media and ICTS constitute the media that changed everything. The truth is the scale with which “alternative facts”, untruths and blatant lies can be spread by people and algorithms, records shows can for the first time threaten democracy and social cohesion at a global scale. “Fake news is now viewed as one of the greatest threats to democracy, journalism and freedom of expression,” (Zhou & Zarafani, 2019, para. 1).

Fake news and the fight against insurgency in Nigeria

One area that has received the negative effect of fake news is the war on insurgency in Nigeria. That is not to say other areas have not felt the downside of the phenomenon. The political space, for example, is also an area that has not been spared. Series of information and counter information crop up on daily basis targeted at different groups. Before now, ethnicity has also been one of the targets and well as driving forces of fake news in Nigeria, but in recent times other numerous factors have been added such as political and religious differences, (AFP, 2019). The Nigerian military fighting insurgency in the North Eastern part of the country as well as other pockets of crimes within the shores of Nigeria always complain about the way people disseminate fake news across various social media platforms. They claim it demoralises officers and men and also hurt the image of the military as they are always painted in bad light, (see Usman, 2018). According to Military authorities, Boko Haram churn out propaganda images and videos that often gets public attention through the help of social media users, (Usman, 2018).

Consequently, the Nigerian Army has always solicited the assistance of the mainstream media to help fight fake news. On daily basis, the social media platforms especially WhatsApp and Facebook are awash with news about attacks on military bases in the North East. Users share and re-share such stories in manners that makes mockery of the military. The military always refute such claims and express how such stories embarrasses officers and men as well as government, and also threatens national security, (Adebajo, 2020). They admit though there may be pockets of cases where the army has been attacked but not on the scale as it is peddled on new media platforms. The Broadcasting Organisation of Nigeria has made attempts at partnering

with the Nigerian Army to fight the menace of fake news in the society especially with regard to the war on insurgency (El-Kurebe, 2019).

Disinformation on social media has become such a problem in Nigeria that it has begun to threaten national security by aggravating existing social divisions and amplifying extreme views. The volume of disinformation now circulating in Nigeria is unprecedented, and has further exacerbated pre-existing ethnic and religious tensions that predate the internet. In 2019, a video that circulated on Facebook and WhatsApp showed Hausa farmers sprinkling insecticide on their beans before they were transported to the southeast of the country. The purpose of this was to preserve the produce from pests such as weevils during the long journey. However, interpretations and voice-overs of the video emerged that drew on longstanding tensions between members of the Hausa and Igbo ethnic groups, claiming that the farmers were sprinkling poison, not insecticide. “The average person who doesn’t bother to ask critical questions or even verify the news would believe this version of the story and share it with others who are also likely to believe and before you know it, there can be a clash between Hausa and Igbos”, (Hassan and Hitchen, 2020, para.7).

Fake News and Political Communication

Nigeria is among the countries in Africa where fake news has had rippling effects. The country’s political landscape is not isolated from the challenge. The issues took a different dimension during the build-up to the 2015 general elections in the country when the then opposition party now ruling – All Progressive Congress (APC) was believed to have used half-truths and fake news to garner support and then won the election. That marked a new era in the outlook for “fake news” in Nigeria, (see Ogaraku, 2020). Political heavyweights now realise the power of the new media (Owkins, 2018). In Nigeria, political parties and politicians now set up special rooms where they have people on their payrolls who work as attack dogs and also dish out information to confuse or convince the people, (BBC News, 2019). The problem with this trend is that it encourages the spread of fake news. Social media influencers are also in the payroll of politicians in Nigeria. reveals that majority of the persons who believe in the powers the new media wields would stop at nothing to mobilise social media influencers to help “dis-inform” and “mis-inform” the public as long as it favors them. It is on record that certain political decisions made by some Nigerians in 2015 and 2019 were influenced as a result of fake news used as a tool, (Irenea, 2017; Cheeseman, 2019).

There are identifiable handles or pages on Twitter and Facebook that are really notorious and once a story is posted by one of them, same story is shared or replicated in about three or four other pages and that is how the reach keeps widening, (Busari, 2019). And this development across new media platforms has taken a dangerous trend. One of such examples is the trending pictures on Facebook of killings in certain part of Nigeria. A quick fact checks reveals that though there may be actual killings

going on elsewhere, most of the photographs circulating on new media platforms are old once being made to look recent with the help of new media technology.

For example, the campaign organisation of the APC was accused by the PDP for spreading false information about Atiku Abubakar during a PDP campaign rally in Sokoto State. Laurretta Onochie, an aide to President Buhari, posted a photo of boxes wrapped together with Nigerian currency notes in the northern state of Sokoto tagged “Keep them in poverty, then give them handouts - Atiku in Sokoto yesterday”. The Buhari campaign organisation denied spreading the false information. However, when the information was investigated by reality checks it was discovered that the photo was two years old and was taken at an event organised by the Kokun Foundation, which campaigns against hunger (<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa>, 2019).

Another widely shared video accuses Atiku Abubakar of brokering a deal with Boko Haram in exchange for land and oil. The short video, viewed over 200,000 times, was shared from a Facebook page called “Make Nigeria Worse Again”. But it has no details about where or when the Atiku campaign was supposed to have announced the plan. The Atiku campaign team told BBC Reality Check that the deal did not exist rather it was a plan by mischief makers to discredit the personality of Atiku Abubakar (<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa>, 2019).

Fake news and Ethno-religious Sentiments in Nigeria

Certain religious groups are involved in the spread of fake news about other religions in order to sow the seed of ethnic sentiment among Nigerians. People use new media technologies to champion ethnic concerns. It is worrisome looking back at the Rwanda genocide. Even in an era where social media presence was not felt in Africa, the use of traditional media with state censorship still snowballed into a full-scale ethnic war that shook the foundation of Rwanda and other African countries.

Nigerian Information Minister, Lai Mohammed was once quoted by *AFP* (2019) to capture his dilemma on what he sees on social media space with regard to ethnic loyalties and religious affiliations thus, “When you go by social media, the impression you get is as if Nigeria is at war and as if Muslims are killing Christians.” What this implies is that Nigerians are sharply divided along ethnic and religious lines and it is affecting the way we relate with one another in the public sphere. More worrisome is the religiosity of Nigerians. Some of them have allowed religious message to permeate their reasoning to the extent of killing because of a certain belief. It is now worse with the advent of new media.

For example, a Facebook post shared in Port Harcourt can cause an uprising in Kano within minutes. Recently, a viral video suggesting that Fulani Herders were killing people with machetes on Benin-Ore road circulated on social media platforms. A quick fact-check proved that it was falsehood, (Olabode, 2020; Olatunji, 2020). But before realising, tensions were high in and around the Hausa/Fulani dominated

areas of Northern Nigeria. It took media organisation such as FRCN and NTA to counter the information and douse tensions with sponsored messages.

For instance, in July 2018, a picture of a woman dressed in traditional Muslim clothes training with an AK-47 rifle was shared on Christian Arise Network, a Nigerian WhatsApp group, with the caption “Fulanis teaching their wives how to handle a gun but we are busy calling on the UN to come and help us.” The post was pastoralists, which has been raging in northern Nigeria since the 1990s. It was however discovered that the picture was fake. The shot was taken from a video that was uploaded on YouTube. The people in the picture spoke neither Hausa nor Fulfulde, the languages spoken by people accused in the post. They sounded like native Arabic speakers, implying that they were not Nigerian. In fact, the description accompanying the video says the woman is Sudanese. Along with outright false reports such as this, there are dangerous exaggerations or distortions of true stories, which are more difficult to spot (Egbunike, 2018).

Fake news and propaganda in Nigeria

Fake news could be deliberately put forwards or ignorantly shared as a form of propaganda to sway public opinion or promote a cause by the governments or its agents. Most leaders and government around the globe are culprits in this regard. Neutrally, propaganda simply means to disseminate or promote particular ideas. Historically, the word meant that until the Roman Catholic established a body to propagate and spread its teachings the world over. “The word later lost its neutrality and subsequent usage has rendered the word pejorative” (Jowett & O’Donnel, 2012 p.3).

Propaganda can equally be seen as a type of persuasion that places emphasis on self-interest. Propagandists falsify or distort facts in order to achieve the purpose of self-interest. Propaganda inflicts political injuries on its victims. Injuries with indelible scars left on the minds of its victims. Jowett and O’Donnel (2012) say propaganda is the deliberate, systematic attempt to shape perceptions, manipulate cognition, and direct behaviour to achieve a response that furthers the desired intent of the propagandist. Propaganda, false flag operations and war advocacy are in the same class of tools used by governments and institutions to achieve set aims and objectives. The traditional media has always been a channel through which government ideas and programmes pass to the public even though at present new media platforms serve as alternatives to the citizens.

One example of a propaganda or false flag operation with suspected government influence is the US Democratic Party hacking of 2016 run up to the 2016 US elections, certain burning issues were up for discussions in the public domain when one of the social media platforms of the presidential candidates of the Democratic Party was hacked. The President, Vladimir Putin and other analysts suggested that the hacking of Hilary Clinton campaign during the election may have been a CIA planned false flag operation designed to implicate Russia, (Zilber, 2017). CNN and

VOA were used mostly as tools to spread the false flag about the hacking, airing commentaries to make the world believe Kremlin was directly involved. A similar example of propaganda championed by organised group is that which Poseti (2013) referred to as “wartime propaganda”. She gave an example of the Taliban sending false and misleading tweets to journalists on the Afghanistan crisis.

Conclusion and Recommendations

There is really no gainsaying the fact that fake news has affected the fabric of the society. The world has come to realise the dangers of fake news and on a daily basis messages are distributed to warn people of the dangers therein. This paper was however, able to establish that the new media has contributed to the spread of fake news and that social media platforms will remain potential instruments for sharing fake news due to the speed or immediacy of the messages and the interactivity feature they possess. It is very instructive to note that if the trend continues unabated without restraint, Nigeria may be plunge into a situation of crisis. In view of the damaging effect of fake news to the society, the following recommendations are hereby made.

- i. People must realise the need for fact-checking. A post is not dangerous until it has been shared and “re-shared”. New media users must realise the enormous influence it wields and therefore take caution while making use of the social media platforms.
- ii. Government should put strategies in place to educate the populace on the dangers of fake news. Strategies such as embarking on special projects through National Orientation Agency (NOA) using specially designed programmes to be aired on national TV aimed at combating the deliberate spread of falsehood. Partnership with NGOs should also be looked into in the fight against deliberate spread of falsehood.
- iii. Facebook and other social media platforms owners must do more than just rhetoric to combat fake news across platforms.
- iv. The fight against the spread of fake news should be the concern of all and sundry if the menace will be tacked in Nigeria. All hands must be on deck to fight the monster. In this regard, stakeholders (government, tech companies, corporate organisation and individuals) must work in unison to achieve victory.

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